

Emerging trends in synthesis of drugs and fine chemicals

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Although, the discovery process for a pharmaceutical product requires management of various biological sciences and organic synthesis, but once a compound has satisfied therapeutic requirements and safety standards, the science involved is essentially organic synthesis, i.e. large-scale manufacture of the compound. Since, any synthesis/manufacture in today's context ought to be green, should not pollute the environment, has to be cost-effective, adheres to safety standards and gives preference for specific stereoisomers, the synthetic scheme one intends to adopt must satisfy and conform to these requirements. A paradigm shift is taking place on how one develops a strategy for synthesis of complex molecules like drugs and fine chemicals. However, many of the syntheses fall short of the requirements. This article reviews the advancement that is taking place in the area of organic synthesis, wherein the modern requirements such as syntheses : (a) achieved in one step, (b) utilising non-hazardous and non-toxic chemicals, (c) which are resource efficient, (d) which are essentially free of solvents and (e) which are enantioselective are described with specific examples from the drugs and fine chemicals sector.

The spectacular advancement made by pharmaceutical industry is essentially because of successful integration of various branches of chemistry, specially synthetic organic chemistry; biological sciences, including biotechnology and informatics. This would be evident from the number of novel therapeutics and diagnostics that are brought into the market-place regularly, essentially because of breathtaking progress not only in biological and chemical sciences but also opening up of newer avenues to understand the disease processes.

The interface between the various disciplines of science is obliterating fast and development of bulk drugs and pharmaceuticals today is a homogenized endeavour. However, amongst all these, synthetic organic chemistry coupled with medicinal chemistry occupies a unique position and this branch of science is perhaps the engine that drives the advancement in the drugs, pharmaceutical and fine chemicals field.

Great strides have been made in synthetic chemistry since 1862 when a serendipitous synthesis of quinine was first reported by Perkin¹. Later on a series of synthesis of the same molecule, all employing different methodologies were reported by Woodward (1944,1945)², Taylor (1972)³, Gutzwiller (1978)⁴, Grethe (1978)⁵, and Imanishi (1982)⁶. A total synthesis of glucose (Fischer, 1890)⁷, tropinone (Robinson, 1917)⁸, hemin (Fischer, 1929)⁹ and equilenin (Bachmann, 1939)¹⁰ endorsed the synthetic chemist's ingenuity in fashioning complex molecules. This was followed by an era where many classical syntheses were achieved. Among these the synthesis of strychnine (1954)¹¹, reserpine (1958)¹², chlorophyll a (1960)¹³, cephalosporin C (1966)¹⁴

and vitamin B₁₂ (1973)¹⁵, all of which evolved out of Woodward's laboratory, remain unmatched even today for their sheer beauty. In fact, Woodward opened vistas for the development of β -lactam antibiotics, which occupy a unique position in the anti-infective segment today. Other than these, there is a legion of elegant and artistic syntheses originating from academic institutions, universities and drug companies, most of which describe chemistry unparalleled. Similarly, great advances have been made in commercial synthesis of many drugs and drug intermediates. This would be evident from the wealth of patent literature describing many improved methods for preparation of practically all drug molecules and its intermediates.

Even though, a synthetic chemist has a wide variety of techniques and methods in his repertoire to tailor an elegant synthesis, however, from the standpoint of his industrial counterpart, most of them suffer from one or more of the following shortcomings. These are : (a) use of hazardous and toxic chemicals, (b) generation of solid/liquid and gaseous effluents, often obnoxious, (c) use of chemicals necessitating special material of construction for processing, (d) use of solvents whose use is frowned upon by International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH), (e) poor regioselectivity/stereospecificity and (f) multiple steps increasing the cost and complexity of operation.

In today's context, it is imperative that any new development in synthesis, especially which would be taken forward for large-scale synthesis, i.e. manufacture has to take into consideration ecological aspects, toxic waste generation, formation of unwanted by-products, cost of manufacture etc. over and above the innovative chemistry employed.

Therefore, the demand today is for a synthesis which (a) is environmentally benign, (b) minimises/eliminates waste generation, (c) uses chemicals which do not call for special material of construction, (d) is 'solvent free' or avoids use of 'environmentally unfriendly' solvents, (e) is regioselective/stereoselective for the desired isomer/enantiomer and (f) telescopes number of steps into a single operation.

The question asked to an industrial chemist today is no longer "can you synthesise the target molecule?" but rather "does your reaction sequence conform to the criteria mentioned hereinbefore?" or "can you bring out a paradigm shift to the approach of synthesis of molecules of industrial importance?"

In view of the above, attempts are being made all over the world to achieve synthesis of target molecules conforming not only to pharmacopoeial/extra-pharmacopoeial quality standards but also through operations which (i) are safe and simple, involving easy isolation of products, (ii) avoid use of costly but use readily available raw materials, (iii) are resource efficient, (iv) afford the product in near quantitative yield, (v) are preferably achieved in one step or minimum number of steps and (vi) are regio/stereo/enantioselective.

The objective of this article is to highlight from the literature the emergent trends in the synthetic area, specially of drugs and fine chemicals.

Safe and simple alternate syntheses

A few examples, wherein an alternate synthesis which scores over the conventional ones in terms of safety, simplicity and eco-friendliness, are given below.

Synthesis of 6-aminopenicillanic and cephalosporanic acid derivatives :

Conventional synthesis of this class of compounds such as 6-APA, 7-ACA, 7-ACCA and 7-ADCA involve deacylation of the corresponding 6- and 7-acylamino precursors chemically using phosphorus pentachloride, a potentially hazardous chemical, requiring necessary safety measures in handling and disposal of waste generation. The same synthesis is achieved today by an enzymatic route¹⁶, which is simple and generates no toxic waste. Many leading manufacturers of these compounds, which are in fact starting points for many of the commercially important β -lactam antibiotics available in the market are investing or have already invested in converting their manufacturing facilities to encompass the enzymatic route.

Ring expansion of a penicillin to a cephalosporin :

This conversion, one of the most widely studied reaction currently utilised in β -lactam chemistry, was first re-

ported by Morin *et al.*¹⁷ who showed that when a five-membered penicillin sulfoxide is heated at elevated temperatures, an intermediate sulfinic acid is formed, which undergoes cyclisation under basic conditions to give the six-membered cephalosporin derivative, viz. 7-ADCA. Numerous modifications of the Morin rearrangement have been effected employing a wide variety of reagents and chemicals for commercial manufacture of 7-ADCA (a valuable intermediate for drugs such as cephalexin, cefadroxil, cephadrine etc.) as well as for the synthesis of 7-ACCA, a key intermediate for the drug, cefaclor. The commercial synthesis of 7-ADCA, involving the Morin rearrangement is illustrated in Scheme 1, which does not fit into the criteria imposed today for a non-hazardous and simple synthesis.

R = Acyl group; R' = Carboxyl protective group

Scheme 1. Conventional synthesis of 7-ADCA through ring expansion by chemical means.

An alternate novel biosynthetic pathway has been developed recently¹⁸ for the synthesis of 7-ADCA. The process that avoids use of hazardous, toxic and expensive chemicals comprises of fermentation of a strain obtained by transformation of a *Penicillium chrysogenum* with a modified expandase gene to yield adipoyl-6-APA, which undergoes ring expansion to adipoyl-7-ADCA and its deacylation with a suitable enzyme gives 7-ADCA, which is recovered from the fermentation broth. The biosynthesis of 7-ADCA achieved in one single operation is depicted in Scheme 2.

Functionalisation at 3- α -position of a cephalosporin derivative :

A new environmentally friendly and safe method¹⁹ developed for preparation of 3-carbamoyl cephalosporin derivatives, such as cefuroxime and its prodrug ester, cefuroxime axetil uses *O-trans-carbamoylase*, an enzyme of microbial origin for the conversion of the 3-hydroxy func-

Scheme 2. Novel biosynthetic process for ring expansion of a penicillin derivative to 7-ADCA

tion to the desired 3-carbamoyl group. This new synthesis replaces the conventional chemical route, which employs hazardous isocyanates, such as dichlorophosphinyl isocyanate²⁰ or chlorosulfinyl isocyanate²¹ to achieve the same conversion (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Process for introducing a carbamoyl function at 3 α -position of a cephalosporin derivative

Synthesis of 3-hydroxycephem derivatives till today is achieved either directly by ozonolysis of the corresponding 3-exomethylene cepham derivative²² or alternately by ozonolysis of a methylene function in an azetidinone derivative²³, the ozonised intermediate, after a couple of functionalisations is finally cyclised in presence of acid to give the target molecule. The chemistry employed is illustrated in Scheme 4.

A new shorter route to 3-hydroxycephems²⁴ from a cor-

Scheme 4. Synthesis of 3-hydroxycephem derivatives through ozonisation

responding penicillin derivative comprises ene-type chlorination of the intermediate azetidinone, which subsequently undergoes C=C bond fission. This homoallylic chloro derivative was cyclised using BiCl₃/Sn or TiCl₄/Sn bimetal redox system, to give the target molecule. The reaction sequence, which obviates the need for ozone is illustrated in Scheme 5

Scheme 5. New 'non-ozone route' to 3-hydroxycephem derivatives

Eco-friendly oxidation :

Oxidation of alcohols to aldehydes or ketones have been traditionally achieved using higher valent chromium or manganese compounds, which create problems in waste disposal. Japanese²⁵ and Belgian²⁶ scientists have now developed environmentally friendly methods for oxidation, which are not only high yielding but generate water as the by-product

In the first case²⁵, the oxidation is carried out using aqueous hydrogen peroxide in the presence of a lipophilic quaternary ammonium hydrogen sulfate as phase transfer catalyst and a tungsten catalyst. A couple of examples using this system is depicted in Scheme 6.

Scheme 6. Eco-friendly (no waste) oxidations catalysed by tungsten.

The second method²⁶, carried out under mild basic conditions, employs copper(I) chloride complexes to phenanthroline and an azo compound or hydrazine, the complex adsorbed on a potassium carbonate support as the oxidant. Oxygen or air is used as the oxidiser. A couple of examples using this system is depicted in Scheme 7.

Scheme 7. Eco-friendly (no waste) oxidations catalysed by copper.

Syntheses, which avoid use of corrosive chemicals

Solid acid catalysts :

There is a sea-change undergoing in the area of catalysis. Traditional homogeneous catalysts are being replaced by solid acids, which hold great promise²⁷. These solid catalysts are environmentally friendly, being non-corrosive do not require special material of construction and are more cost-effective and economically viable.

Manufacture of cumene, an important intermediate for numerous fine chemicals such as acetone, phenol etc., till today utilised catalysts based on phosphoric acids, which caused serious corrosion and waste disposal problems. This problem has been solved successfully by the use of solid acid catalysts, viz. catalysts based on modernite or zeolites²⁷.

Use of polymer supported (immobilized) Lewis acid catalysts or microencapsulated Lewis acids :

These are replacing the traditional corrosive monomeric Lewis acids in many reactions. Kobayashi and his team at the University of Tokyo have extensively studied the use of these catalysts in a wide range of organic reactions. In such type of supported catalysts, the Lewis acid is physically enveloped by polymer thin films and stabilised by interaction between π -electrons of benzene rings of the polysty-

rene used as a polymer backbone and vacant orbitals of the Lewis acid. Microencapsulated Lewis acids have been used in Michael reaction²⁸, Mannich type reactions²⁹, Diels-Alder reaction³⁰, Strecker reaction³¹, Friedel-Crafts acylation³², imino-aldol reaction³³, quinone forming reactions³⁴ and cyanation³¹ and allylation³⁵ reactions of aldimines. These catalysts which can be prepared easily have higher activity than the monomeric acids and are easily recoverable and reusable. A few examples where these catalysts have found application is provided in Scheme 8.

Michael reaction²⁸ :

Yield : 1st use (92%), 2nd use (97%), 3rd use (95%)

[MCS(OTf)₃] = Microencapsulated scandium trifluoromethanesulfonate

Friedel-Crafts acylation³² :

Yield : 1st use (76%), 2nd use (76%), 3rd use (81%)

Mannich type reaction²⁹ :

Yield : 1st use (90%), 2nd use (96%), 3rd use (93%)

Imino Aldol reaction³³ :

Yield : 1st use (90%), 2nd use (90%), 3rd use (88%), 4th use (89%), 5th use (89%), 6th use (88%), 7th use (90%)

Scheme 8. Reactions using microencapsulated Lewis acids.

New process for manufacture of LABs :

The traditional catalyst, viz. hydrogen fluoride, an extremely corrosive, hazardous and toxic chemical used in the production of linear alkylbenzenes (LABs), has been successfully replaced by a solid acid catalyst, viz. fluorided silica-alumina catalyst³⁶, which does not require special material of construction, involves lower operating costs and obviates the need for an acid scrubbing system and waste disposal of calcium fluoride.

Resource efficient syntheses

Oxidation of alkenes :

In conventional oxidation of alkenes with molecular

oxygen carried out in the presence of oxidising agents such as peracids, chlorates, periodates etc. effectively only one oxygen atom is incorporated into the molecule, the other one reacts with a reducing agent leading to by-products. Now systems have been developed wherein both the oxygen atoms get utilised in the oxidation, when carried out in the presence of certain catalysts. This has been demonstrated elegantly by Groves and Quinn³⁷ during the epoxidation of an alkene in the presence of a porphyrin-ruthenium catalyst (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9. Efficient oxidation of an alkene with molecular oxygen in presence of a catalyst.

A highly chemo- and enantioselective osmium-catalysed dihydroxylation³⁸, which is an improvement over the Sharpless method, has been reported for the first time, wherein the oxidation is carried out in the presence of molecular oxygen. Thus, 1-octene is converted to the diol under mild conditions in excellent yields (Scheme 10). Moreover, the catalyst used can be recycled.

Scheme 10. Chemo- and enantioselective dihydroxylation of an alkene in presence of molecular oxygen.

Phase separable homogeneous catalysis or aqueous homogeneous catalysis :

It is another emerging area gaining prominence in industrial application. Here, the active catalyst for the reaction remains dissolved in water so that the reactants and the reaction product/s, generally organic in nature and non-polar get separated off easily at the end of the reaction from the catalyst solution. Importantly, easy reuse of the catalyst is ensured.

This concept has recently been employed in the palladium catalysed Suzuki coupling³⁹, which till now could be initiated only when expensive brominated or iodinated substrates are used. It is now possible to achieve the same using less expensive chlorinated analogues when the reaction is mediated by catalysts based on Pd/TPPTS (triply *meta*-sulfonated triphenylphosphine) in an aqueous environment. The coupled products thus obtained are valuable intermediates for synthesis of antihypertensives such as losartan and valsartan (Scheme 11).

Similarly, the Heck reaction consisting of reaction of aryl halides with olefins in presence of palladium catalysts is

Scheme 11. Resource efficient Suzuki coupling

restricted to expensive iodo derivatives, making its industrial application a rare proposition. However, it has been demonstrated recently that the less expensive chlorides and bromides could be made to undergo the reaction using palladium catalysts, such as Pd(OAc)₂ or PdCl₂ in the presence of tetraphenylphosphonium salts, Ph₄PX (X = Cl, Br, I)⁴⁰. The chemistry is illustrated in Scheme 12.

Scheme 12. Resource efficient Heck reaction involving coupling of styrene and chlorobenzene.

Syntheses free of solvents or which avoid use of environmentally unfriendly solvents

A few decades back it would have been difficult to imagine that one could carry out a synthesis without taking recourse to a solvent medium (i.e. solid state reaction). Chemists have gleefully used solvents in practically all syntheses, never realising that some of these could be 'environmentally unfriendly'. But times are changing. Stringent measures are being taken by environmental authorities and other regulatory bodies against those using solvents and those whose finished products contain trace solvents, frowned upon by International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH)⁴¹. It is therefore, a great challenge to chemists to achieve a synthesis in the solid state, without the use of solvents. Fortunately, the development of microwave ovens, and ultrasonic baths and reactors have simplified the chemist's job and one can see a number of syntheses carried out using these appliances. A few such syntheses are illustrated here.

Wittig reaction :

This reaction has been conducted in a domestic microwave oven on mere admixture of the reactants in the absence of a solvent⁴² (Scheme 13). The reaction gave better yield of the product compared to the one wherein conventional solvents were used and moreover, involved shorter duration times.

Synthesis of allylic alcohols : This has been achieved under 'no solvent' conditions, e.g. ring opening of a sulfonate ester of an oxiranemethanol in presence of a tellurium catalyst gave the allylic alcohol, viz. (3*S*)-(+)-linalool in 95% ee⁴³ (Scheme 14).

Scheme 13. Wittig reaction carried out in a microwave oven in absence of solvent.

Scheme 14. Synthesis of allylic alcohols under 'no solvent' conditions.

Radical addition reaction :

Radical addition of alkyl α -iodocarboxylates and α -iodoalkanenitriles to alkenes, initiated by electron transfer from copper metal has been achieved in the absence of a solvent, by simply heating the reactants at 100–130° in an inert atmosphere⁴⁴ (Scheme 15).

Scheme 15. Radical addition reaction in the absence of a solvent.

Oxidation reactions :

A new catalytic system consisting of Na_2WO_4 dihydrate, aminomethyl phosphonic acid and methylene *n*-octylammonium hydrogensulfate is used for oxidation of alcohols as well as epoxidation of terminal olefins under halide-free and solvent-free conditions, generating little waste^{45,46} (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16. Oxidation of alcohols and alkenes in absence of solvent.

Solid state borohydride reduction :

Reduction of ketones to alcohols using sodium borohydride in the solid state has been achieved by allowing a finely

powdered mixture of the ketone and a ten-fold excess amount of the hydride reagent to remain in a dry-box at room temperature for five days⁴⁷ (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17. Solid state borohydride reduction of ketones.

Lipase catalysed esterification :

A convenient solvent-free large-scale enzymatic process has been developed to prepare a series of glucoside esters from glucopyranosides in high yields. The conversion is achieved by simple mixing of the starting glycoside with a fatty acid at 70° in the presence of an immobilized lipase⁴⁸ (Scheme 18).

Scheme 18. Enzymatic esterification of glycosides in absence of solvents.

Reactions in aqueous media :

Kobayashi and his team have designed synthetic reactions (normally requiring solvent mediation) which can be carried out in aqueous media⁴⁹, i.e. an environmentally friendly chemical process.

A classical example is the Strecker reaction, employing trimethylsilylcyanide (TMSCN) as the source of cyano anions which has to be carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions, since TMSCN is susceptible to hydrolysis in presence of water. Kobayashi⁵⁰ has developed a method by which the same reaction can be carried out in presence of a solvent as well as in an aqueous medium, which obviates the need for use of TMSCN. Tributyltin cyanide, which is stable to water is used as a potential source of cyanate ions. The reaction is catalysed by scandium triflate and has been used successfully for conversion of aromatic, aliphatic, heterocyclic as well as α,β -unsaturated aldehydes to the corresponding α -aminonitriles, in high yields. The most important aspect of the reaction is that higher yields are achieved when the reaction is carried out in water compared to solvents. Moreover, complete recovery of tin compounds is achieved, eliminating waste disposal problems. A typical Strecker reaction utilising the Kobayashi conditions is de-

Scheme 19. Scandium triflate-catalysed Strecker reaction carried out in aqueous media.

picted in Scheme 19.

Use of ionic liquids :

These are finding wide applications as 'environmentally friendly' substitute for conventional solvents in many reactions. Ionic liquids typically consist of nitrogen containing organic cations and inorganic anions, whose chemical and physical properties can be fine tuned for a wide range of applications⁵¹. These are easy to prepare, are fluids at room temperature, stable to moisture and have no detectable vapour pressure. Its unique solvating properties enhances its recyclability. Ambient temperature ionic liquids are finding use as solvents in polymerisation reactions, hydrogenations, and as catalysts for Diels-Alder reaction.

A Friedel-Crafts reaction using the ambient temperature ionic liquid, viz. [emim]⁺Cl-AlCl₃, viz. [1-methyl-3-ethylimidazolium chloride-aluminium chloride] has been reported to work very efficiently in comparison to conventional solvents, providing the stereoelectronically favoured product⁵² (Scheme 20).

Scheme 20. A Friedel-Crafts acylation using ionic liquids.

Regioselective alkylation of indole and 2-naphthol which are solvent-dependent, generally necessitating the use of dipolar aprotic solvents such as DMF, is now achieved by use of an ionic liquid [bmim][PF₆]⁵³. The alkylated products

are obtained in good regioselectivity. Moreover, the method is simple and the products are isolated easily (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21. Regioselective alkylation of indole and 2-naphthol using an ionic liquid.

Reactions carried out in supercritical carbon dioxide :

More and more reactions are being carried out in supercritical fluids, which obviates waste disposal problems. These also offer other advantages such as controlling the phase behaviour of products, increased reaction rates and better efficiency. Organometallic compounds have been synthesised, metal chelation and extractions have been achieved, inorganic nanoparticles have been prepared and lipase catalysed reactions have been carried out, all using supercritical carbon dioxide⁵⁴.

It has been shown⁵⁵ that higher selectivity is achieved in the enantioselective hydrogenation of α -enamides to α -amino acids when supercritical carbon dioxide is employed in comparison to cases where conventional solvents are used (Scheme 22). This has immense potential in 'green' drug

Scheme 22. An asymmetric catalytic hydrogenation carried out in supercritical carbon dioxide.

synthesis. Moreover, ibuprofen having an enantiomeric purity >90% has been synthesised by lipase-catalysed esterification of the racemic compound in supercritical carbon dioxide⁵⁶ (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23. Enantioselective esterification of ibuprofen in supercritical carbon dioxide.

Regio/stereo/enantioselective synthesis

Most of the optically active drugs available currently in the market are a mixture of two enantiomers, i.e. in the form of racemates. Enantiomers, apart from giving non-superimposable mirror images are not identical in their behaviour towards polarised light and towards chiral molecules of life such as proteins and nucleic acids. It is now known that one of the single enantiomer present in the racemate may actually be contributing to the efficacy of the drug, the other one either having no efficacy, or may acutely be toxic or may cause adverse side-effects in the patient. The most famous case in history is the administration of thalidomide (meant as a sedative) to pregnant women during the late fifties, which resulted in the birth of children with deformity. Today, everybody knows that the (*S*)-form of this drug is teratogenic, responsible for the adverse effects whereas the (*R*)-form is actually the sedative. Other examples wherein the two enantiomers have opposite effects are : whereas (*S*)-dopa is effective in the treatment of Parkinson's disease, administration of the (*R*)-form causes serious side-effects; the (*S*)-form of ketamine is an anaesthetic, whereas the (*R*)-form is an hallucinogen; the (*S,S*)-isomer of ethambutol is a tuberculostatic, whereas the (*R,R*)-isomer causes blindness.

In view of the above, there is a growing concern among health authorities to approve the 'desired enantiomer' only as a drug and one could see great emphasis being laid by all pharmaceutical manufacturers to introduce a single chiral entity as the drug candidate. Today, a single enantiomeric species is 'in thing', replacing the racemate drugs of yeasty years. This has resulted in a paradigm shift in the approach of chemists towards synthesis of these chiral compounds. The traditional chemist had depended upon resolution of the racemic mixture to isolate the pure individual isomers. This involved considerable loss of the precious desired isomer in processing. The emergent trend, on the other hand, is to achieve a regio/stereo/enantioselective synthesis through various divergent methods to obtain the right enantiomer/isomer in high purity (ee) and yield, thereby

minimising the losses. Synthetic development in this area has seen increased activity in the last few decades as can be seen by the explosion of publications, both academic and patent on enantioselective synthesis. A few such important syntheses in this area are highlighted below.

An asymmetric Strecker reaction :

This reaction has been achieved⁵⁷, wherein the enantioselectivity in the addition of a cyanide to imines to give α -amino acids has been enhanced by use of a chiral salen catalyst, viz. aluminium(III) chelated by a double Schiff base of single isomer of *trans*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane with 3,5-di-*tert*-2-hydroxy-benzaldehyde. The final product was obtained in an enantiomeric pure form (>99%). The chemistry employed is depicted in Scheme 24. The other advantages of using a salen catalyst are : (i) the catalyst loading is low, (ii) the catalyst can be prepared easily and (iii) it has an indefinite shelf-life under ambient conditions.

Scheme 24. An highly enantioselective Strecker reaction using a salen catalyst.

An industrial process for manufacture of (*S*)-DOPA :

This process for preparation of (*S*)-dopa, useful in the treatment of Parkinson's disease, utilises a rhodium-catalysed highly enantioselective hydrogenation in one of the key steps⁵⁸ (Scheme 25).

Synthesis of cilastatin :

A chiral copper carbenoid reaction of alkyl diazoacetate with an olefin, utilises a chiral copper complex for the asymmetric synthesis of cyclopropane carboxylic acids, in high enantiomeric purity. This has been utilised for synthesis of (*S*)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid^{59,60}, a key intermediate for cilastatin, which is a dehydropeptidase in-

Scheme 25. Industrial manufacture of (S)-dopa

hibitor administered in combination with potent carbapenems, especially imipenem. The chemistry employed is illustrated in Scheme 26.

Scheme 26. Enantioselective synthesis of cilastatin

Enantioselective synthesis of indinavir sulfate :

The process chemistry for synthesis of indinavir sulfate (Crixivan[®]), an HIV protease inhibitor, containing five chiral centres in the molecule till now utilised an expensive multi-step chemical sequence. The innovators, Merck & Co., have now developed an enantioselective method for synthesis of a key intermediate, viz. *cis*-aminoindanol in >99% ee starting from indene by employing a chiral salen catalyst system⁶¹ (Scheme 27). Reports are there that Merck is also trying to develop a metabolically engineered fermentation method for synthesis of the intermediate.

Scheme 27. Enantioselective synthesis of indinavir sulfate

Other methods .

Several other enantioselective synthetic methods such as enzymatic catalysis or biocatalysis⁶², dynamic kinetic resolutions⁶³, use of chiral adjuvants⁶⁴ and chiral auxiliaries⁶⁵ etc. are being used increasingly today for obtaining the desired enantiomeric species in high purity (ee). Industrial synthesis using such methods has been recently published⁶⁶.

The most recent trend is to utilise combinatorial chemistry for discovery of new enantioselective methods and enantioselective catalysts⁶⁷. Two approaches have been developed. The first one involves creation of various arrays of binding elements (grouped spatially) in a known ligand structure, which are then evaluated for their individual efficiency⁶⁸. The second one consists of creation of potential ligand libraries, having no predefined binding sites. Further studies are conducted to evaluate the efficacy of the numerous candidates as enantioselective catalysts⁶⁹.

Multistep syntheses in one operation

Most of the methods reported in literature today involve multiple steps for synthesis of the target molecule. Under ideal conditions a synthesis ought to be achieved in one step or utilising minimum number of steps. Some of the recent advances in this direction are summarised below.

Single step synthesis of corrin :

A biosynthetic process employing a combination of twelve enzymes has been reported to convert α -aminovaleric acid to corrin in one step in 20% yield⁷⁰ (Scheme 28).

 Scheme 28. One step conversion of α -aminovaleric acid to corrin

Taxadiene synthesis :

The enzyme, taxadiene synthase has been shown to cyclise geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate in one step to taxadiene⁷¹, a key intermediate for the anticancer drug, taxol (Scheme 29).

Synthesis of erythromycin derivatives .

Reactions catalysed by an engineered DEBS KS1 null mutant convert cysteamine derivatives directly to erythromycin derivatives⁷² (Scheme 30).

Scheme 29. Enzymatic cyclisation reaction in synthesis of taxadiene.

Scheme 30. Plasmid engineered synthesis of erythromycin derivatives.

Synthesis of cefaclor :

The cephalosporin antibiotic, cefaclor is obtained in one step from cephalixin on treatment with hydrogen peroxide and a protein extract derived from *Rathayibacter biopureis*⁷³ (Scheme 31). This is an important alternative method, which could replace quite a few chemical steps involved in synthesis of cefaclor.

Scheme 31. Enzymatic synthesis of cefaclor.

The other emerging trend is the 'Cascade Synthesis', where several multiple steps in a synthetic sequence are condensed into a single operation, utilising carbanion, carbene, radical or organometallic chemistry.

Cationic cascade reaction :

In this reaction a fluorinated polyolefin undergoes biomimetic cyclisation to form a pentacyclic compound, a key intermediate for the pentacyclic triterpenoid, β -amyrin. This conversion in which four new bonds and seven stereocentres are formed proceeds in 65–70% yield⁷⁴ (Scheme 32).

Scheme 32. A cationic cascade sequence in the synthesis of β -amyrin.

Radical cascade reaction :

An intermediate for lysergic acid was obtained by a triple radical cyclisation reaction (radical cascade) of an enamine with Bu₃SnH in 20% yield, wherein three new bonds and three stereocentres were formed⁷⁵ (Scheme 33).

Scheme 33. A radical cascade synthesis of LSD.

Pericyclic cascade reaction :

In this reaction a bis-furan derivative undergoes two simultaneous Diels-Alder additions with a bis-dienophile to give the adduct, which gives optically active diols on further transformation. The addition achieved under pressure creates four new bonds and eight stereocentres⁷⁶ (Scheme 34).

Scheme 34. A pericyclic cascade synthesis.

Mixed cascade synthesis :

The other emerging strategy is the 'mixed cascade synthesis' or 'polyconvergent strategies', wherein several different types of bond forming events are choreographed into one operation. Thus, a tetracyclisation process to obtain a pentacyclic amine, an intermediate for C-30 daphniphyllum alkaloids in 82% yield, has been reported⁷⁷ (Scheme 35).

Scheme 35. A mixed cascade synthesis.

Multi-component synthesis :

A seven multi-component reaction (7-MCR) has been reported for the first time⁷⁸ as illustrated in Scheme 36. Multi-component reactions are those wherein the product is

obtained in one-pot by reacting at least three different starting materials, having different functional groups. The product incorporates substantial portions of these reagents or starting materials. The reaction proceeds by the Zipper principle, i.e. each reaction step is a prerequisite for the next stage.

Scheme 36. A seven component condensation reaction

Polyconvergent synthesis :

A polyconvergent or a multisite synthesis, i.e. modifications made in several functional groups in the course of a single operation, has been demonstrated⁷⁹. Thus, squalene on asymmetric dihydroxylation with an osmium catalyst and a co-oxidant undergoes polyhydroxylation to a dodecahydroxy derivative as a single enantiomer in high yields. It is remarkable to note that the reaction proceeds with twelve chemical and stereochemical events taking place in tandem and only one out of the thirtysix possible stereoisomers is produced (Scheme 37).

Scheme 37. Polyhydroxylation of squalene in one step

Conclusion

From the above, one could see that research in drugs and fine chemicals is passing through a very exciting phase today, with emphasis on a synthesis which is cost-effective, resource-efficient and eco-friendly. Eventhough, most of the demands are being met, there are still areas where vast improvements are desired. This is especially true when one considers the synthesis of many important drugs. The following two examples, albeit not exhaustive should help one to appreciate the need for such a synthesis.

Synthesis of clarithromycin :

This semisynthetic macrolide antibiotic (compound B, Scheme 38) with a world sales of 1.25 billion dollars in

1999, is synthesised by several methods, all of which essentially involve methylation of the 6-hydroxy function of erythromycin A (compound A, Scheme 38). However, to achieve the methylation, all the reported methods⁸⁰ take recourse to protections and deprotections of the various functional groups, especially in the 9, 2', 3, 4'' positions of the molecule, resulting in number of steps, lower yields of the end-product (not more than 45–50%) and use of costly and hazardous chemicals.

Scheme 38. Clarithromycin from erythromycin A

The question is "Can one fashion a synthesis wherein clarithromycin is obtained from erythromycin A or other suitable starting materials ideally in one single step?"

Synthesis of simvastatin :

This drug (compound C, Scheme 39), an important HMG CoA reductase inhibitor differs from its analogue, lovastatin (compound D, Scheme 39) in that it has an additional methyl group in the 2-position of the molecule. Even today the drug is synthesised from lovastatin, wherein the methylation is achieved either by a very lengthy circuitous route⁸¹ or by a shorter route which, however, involves utilisation of very low temperatures upto -78°C ⁸².

Here again the question is "Can the methylation be achieved in a single step?"

The demand for an 'optimum synthesis' is hanging like a Democle's sword over the heads of synthetic chemists. To achieve such a goal, a more paradigmatic approach is desired from the chemist who like a conductor in a musical

Scheme 39. Simvastatin from lovastatin.

symphony should be able to wield his baton (utilising all the techniques available in his repertoire or evolve newer techniques) to produce a synergetic effect, which would not only extend the frontiers of synthetic chemistry but usher in an era of 'green chemistry'.

References

1. W. H. Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1862, 232.
2. R. B. Woodward and W. E. Doering, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 849; 1945, 67, 860.
3. E. C. Taylor and S. F. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 6218.
4. J. Gutzwiller and M. R. Uskokovi'c, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 100, 576.
5. G. Grethe, H. L. Lee, T. Mitt and M. R. Uskokovi'c, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 100, 589.
6. T. Imanishi, M. Iuoue, Y. Wada and M. Hanaoka, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1982, 30, 1925.
7. E. Fischer, *Chem. Ber.*, 1890, 23, 799.
8. R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 762.
9. H. Fischer, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1929, 468, 98.
10. W. E. Bachmann, W. Cole and A. L. Wilds, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 974.
11. R. B. Woodward, M. P. Cava, W. D. Ollis, A. Hunger, H. U. Daeniker and K. Schenker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4749.
12. R. B. Woodward, F. E. Bader, H. Bickel, A. J. Frey and R. W. Kierstead, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2023; *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 2, 1.
13. R. B. Woodward, W. A. Ayer, J. M. Beaton, F. Bickelhaupt, R. Bonnett, P. Buchschacher, G. L. Closs, H. Dutler, J. Harnah, F. P. Hauck, S. Ito, A. Langemann, E. Le Goff, W. Leimgruber, W. Lwowski, J. Sauer, Z. Valenta and H. Vol, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3800; R. B. Woodward, *Angew. Chem.*, 1960, 72, 651.
14. R. B. Woodward, K. Heusler, J. Gosteli, P. Naegeli, W. Oppolzer, R. Ramage, S. Ranganathan and H. Vorbruggen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 852.
15. R. B. Woodward, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1973, 33, 145.
16. A. Bruggink, E. C. Roos and E. de Vroom, *Org. Proc. Res. Dev.*, 1998, 2, 128.
17. R. B. Morin, B. G. Jackson, R. A. Mueller, E. R. Lavagnino, W. B. Scanlon and S. L. Andrews, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1896; 1969, 91, 1401; R. B. Morin and B. G. Jackson, US Pat. 3275626/1966 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 65, 20133).
18. J. E. Dotfiaz and W. -K. Yeh, EP Pat. 366354 B1/1996 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, 114, 38437); M. J. Conder, L. Carwford, P. C. McAda and J. A. Rambossek, EP Pat. 532341/1998 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, 118, 253401 and 1994, 121, 229008); M. J. Conder, J. A. Rambossek, A. M. Stepan, P. C. McAda, L. Crawford and C. D. Reeves, EP Pat. 540210/1998 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, 119, 93725); R. A. L. Bovenberg, B. P. Koekman, A. Hockema, J. M. Van der Laan and J. Verweij, PCT Pat. WO 95/04148/1995 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, 122, 289045); PCT Pat. WO 95/04149/1995 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, 122, 289042); R. A. L. Bovenberg, J. M. Van der Laan, R. Kerkman and M. Nieboer, PCT Pat. WO 98/02551/1998 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1998, 128, 151115).
19. I. D. Fleming, M. K. Turner and S. J. Brewer, US Pat. 4075061/1978 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 168488); US Pat. 4164447/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 168488).
20. D. C. Humber, S. B. Laing and G. G. Weingarten, US Pat. 4284767/1981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 95, 43147). Also *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, 93, 46694 and 1980, 92, 46208.
21. H. J. White, D. T. Eastlick and J. E. Oughton, US Pat. 4775750/1988 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1985, 103, 53862).
22. R. B. Chauvette, US Pat. 3925372/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 84, 105620).
23. T. Tsuji, Y. Hamashima, M. Yoshioka, M. Narisada, H. Tanida, T. Komeno and W. Nageta, US Pat. 4160085/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, 98, 89062). Also *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 86, 55466.
24. H. Tanaka, M. Taniguchi, Y. Kameyama, M. Monnin, M. Sasaoka, T. Shiroy, S. Nagao and S. Torii, *Chem. Lett.*, 1990, 1867.
25. K. Sato, M. Aoki, J. Takagi and R. Noyori, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, 119, 12386.
26. I. E. Marko, P. R. Gilès, M. Tsukazaki, S. M. Brown and C. J. Urch, *Science*, 1996, 274, 2044.
27. J. A. Horsley, *Chemtech*, Oct. 1997, 45.
28. S. Kobayashi, I. Hachiya, H. Ishitani and M. Araki, *Synlett*, 1993, 472; S. Kobayashi and S. Nagayama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, 120, 2985.
29. S. Kobayashi, M. Araki and M. Yasuda, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, 36, 5773.
30. S. Kobayashi, I. Hachiya, M. Araki and H. Ishitani, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1993, 34, 3755.
31. S. Kobayashi, H. Ishitani and M. Ueno, *Synlett*, 1997, 115.
32. A. Kawada, S. Mitamura and S. Kobayashi, *Synlett*, 1994, 545.
33. S. Kobayashi, M. Araki, H. Ishitani, S. Nagayama and S. Hachiya, *Synlett*, 1995, 233.
34. S. Kobayashi, H. Ishitani and S. Nagayama, *Chem. Lett.*, 1995, 423.
35. S. Kobayashi and S. Nagayama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, 119, 10049.
36. J. A. Kocal, US Pat. 5196574/1993 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, 118, 236451). Also *Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, 122, 31103.

37. J. T. Groves and R. Quinn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 5790.
38. C. Dobler, G. Mehlretter and M. Beller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1999, **38**, 3026.
39. B. Cornils, *Org. Proc. Res. Dev.*, 1998, **2**, 121.
40. M. T. Reetz, G. Lohmer and R. Schwickardi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1998, **37**, 481.
41. A committee concerned with harmonisation of technical requirements for the registration of pharmaceutical products among three regions, viz. The European Union, Japan and the United States. The committee consists of members drawn from individual health and regulatory bodies and industrial federations.
42. A. Spinella, T. Fortunati and A. Soriente, *Synlett*, 1997, 93.
43. Q. Xu, B. Chao, Y. Wang and D. C. Dittmer, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 12131.
44. J. O. Metzger and R. Mahler, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1995, **34**, 902; J. O. Metzger, R. Mahler and G. Francke, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1997, 2303.
45. K. Sato, M. Aoki, J. Takagi and R. Noyori, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 12386.
46. K. Sato, M. Aoki and M. Ogawa, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 8310; K. Sato, M. Aoki, M. Ogawa, T. Hashimoto, D. Panyella and R. Noyori, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1997, **70**, 905.
47. F. Toda, K. Kiyoshige and M. Yagi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1989, **28**, 320.
48. K. Adelhorst, F. Bjorkling, S. Godtfredsen and O. Kirk, *Synthesis*, 1990, 112.
49. S. Kobayashi, T. Wakayashi, S. Nagayama and H. Oyamada, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 4559; S. Kobayashi, T. Wakabayashi and H. Oyamada, *Chem. Lett.*, 1997, 831; S. Kobayashi, T. Busujima and S. Nagayama, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 19; S. Kobayashi in "Organic Reactions in Water", ed. P. Grieco, Chapman and Hall, London, 1997.
50. S. Kobayashi, T. Busujima and S. Nagayama, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 981.
51. M. Freemantle, *Chem. Eng. News*, March 30, 1998, 32.
52. C. J. Adams, M. J. Earle, G. Roberts and K. R. Seddon, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 2097.
53. M. J. Earle, P. B. McCormac and K. R. Seddon, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 2245.
54. J. O. Metzger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1998, **37**, 2975.
55. C. M. Wai, F. Hunt, M. Ji and X. Chen, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1998, **75**, 1641.
56. O. Aaltonen and M. Rantakylä, in "Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium on Supercritical Fluids", ed. M. A. McHugh, Department of Chemical Engineering, John Hopkins University, Baltimore, 1991, p. 146.
57. M. S. Sigman and E. N. Jacobsen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **120**, 5315; S. C. Stinson, *Chem. Eng. News*, June 1, 1998, 15.
58. W. S. Knowles, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1983, **16**, 106.
59. T. Aratani, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1995, **57**, 1839.
60. R. Noyori, *Science*, 1990, **248**, 1194.
61. C. H. Senanayake, G. B. Smith, K. M. Ryan, L. E. Fredenburgh, J. Liu, F. E. Roberts, D. L. Hughes, R. D. Larsen, T. R. Verhoeven and P. J. Reider, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 3271.
62. C. H. Wong and G. M. Whitesides, "Enzymes in Synthetic Organic Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1994; S. West in "Speciality Chemicals : Innovations in Industrial Synthesis and Applications", ed. B. Pearson, Elsevier, London, 1991, pp 499-507, B. L. Bray, M. D. Goodyear, J. J. Partridge and D. J. Tapolczay in "Chirality in Industry II", eds. A. N. Collins, G. N. Sheldrake and J. Crosby, Wiley Chichester, 1997, pp 41-78.
63. S. Yamada, Y. Mori, K. Morimatsu, Y. Ishizu, Y. Ozaki, R. Yashioka T. Nakatani and H. Seko, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 8586.
64. M. J. O'Donnell in "Catalytic Asymmetric Synthesis", ed. I. Ojima, VCH Publishers, New York, 1993, pp. 389-411; U. H. Dolling, D. L. Hughes, A. Bhattacharya, K. M. Ryan, S. Karady, L. M. Weinstock and E. J. J. Grabowski in "Phase Transfer Catalysis", ACS Symposium Series 326, ed. C. M. Starks, ACS, Washington, 1987, pp. 67-81; E. J. Corey, R. K. Bakshi and S. Shibata, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 5551; S. E. Denmark, K. T. Wong and R. A. Stavenger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 2333.
65. A. J. McKenzie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 1249; V. Prelog, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 308; J. R. Gage and D. A. Evans, *Org. Synth.*, 1989, **68**, 77; M. Braun and S. Graef, *Org. Synth.*, 1993, **72**, 38; D. J. Ager, I. Prakash and D. R. Schaad, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 835; *Aldrichimica Acta*, 1997, **30**, 3; T. Mukiyama, *Aldrichimica Acta*, 1996, **29**, 59; M. S. Hoekstra, D. M. Sobieray, M. A. Schwindt, T. A. Mulhern, T. M. Grote, B. K. Huckabee, V. S. Hendrickson, L. C. Franklin, E. J. Granger and G. L. Karrick, *Org. Process R&D*, 1997, **1**, 26; P. J. Harrington and E. Lodewijk, *Org. Process R&D*, 1997, **1**, 72.
66. "Process Chemistry in the Pharmaceutical Industry", ed. K. G. Gadamasetti, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1999.
67. S. Borman, *Chem. Eng. News*, 1997, **75** (8), 43; R. Baum, *Chem. Eng. News*, 1996, **74** (7), 28; L. A. Thompson and J. A. Ellman, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 555; R. W. Armstrong, A. P. Combs, P. A. Tempest, S. D. Brown and T. A. Keating, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1996, **29**, 123; K. Burgess, H. J. Lim, A. M. Porte and G. A. Sulikowski, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1996, **35**, 220; P. Murray-Rust, H. S. Rzepa and B. J. Whitaker, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1997, **26**, 1; J. H. Krieger, *Chem. Eng. News*, 1997, **75** (19), 30.
68. M. T. Burger and W. C. Still, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 7382
69. M. B. Francis, N. S. Finney and E. N. Jacobsen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 8983.
70. C. A. Roessner and A. I. Scott, *Chem. Biol.*, 1996, **3**, 325.
71. J. Hefner, S. M. Rubenstein, R. E. B. Ketchum, D. M. Gibson, R. M. Roberts and R. Croteau, *Chem. Biol.*, 1996, **3**, 479.
72. J. R. Jacobsen, C. R. Hutchinson, D. E. Cane and C. Khosla, *Science*, 1997, **277**, 367
73. B. L. Wong, Y. -Q. Shen and Y. -P. Chen, US Pat. 5589354/1996 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1996, **125**, 10881); US Pat. 5695951/1997 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1998, **128**, 30380).
74. W. S. Johnson, M. S. Plummer, S. P. Reddy and W. R. Bartlett, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 515.

75. D. E. Cladingboel and P. J. Parsons, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1543.
76. C. Marchionni and P. Vogel, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, 37, 4149.
77. C. H. Heathcock, M. M. Hansen, R. B. Ruggeri and J. C. Kath, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, 57, 2544.
78. A. Dömling and I. Ugi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1993, 32, 563.
79. G. A. Crispino, P. T. Ho and K. B. Sharpless, *Science*, 1993, 259, 64.
80. Y. Watanabe, S. Morimoto and S. Omura, US Pat. 4331803/1982 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, 96, 143261); H. Faubl and R. G. Stein, US Pat. 4640910/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 106, 188998); Y. Watanabe, S. Morimoto, M. Gori, M. Mitsukuchi, T. Adachi, J. Nakagami, T. Asaka, T. Eguchi and K. Sota, US Pat. 4672109/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, 104, 186804); S. Morimoto, T. Adachi, T. Asaka, M. Kasimura, Y. Watanabe and K. Sota, US Pat. 4670549/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 106, 5375); S. Morimoto, T. Adachi, T. Matsunga, M. Kashimura, T. Asaka, Y. Watanabe and K. Sota, US Pat. 4680386/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, 105, 79305); US Pat. 4990602/1991 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, 110, 173696); Y. Misawa, T. Asaka, M. Kashimura, S. Morimoto, Y. Watanabe and K. Hatayama, US Pat. 5302705/1994 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, 115, 72146); S. Morimoto, T. Adachi, T. Matsunga, M. Kashimura, Y. Watanabe and K. Sota, EP Pat. 260938/1992 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, 109, 6898).
81. A. K. Willard and R. L. Smith, *J. Labelled Compd. Radiopharm.*, 1982, 19, 337; D. Askin, T. R. Verhoeven, T. M.-H. Liu and I. Shinkai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, 56, 4929; R. L. Monaghan, A. W. Alberts, C. H. Hoffman and G. Alberts-Schonberg, US Pat. 4231938/1980 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 101307). Also *Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 94, 190313; 1982, 97, 22084 and 1982, 97, 214252.
82. M. Sletzinger, T. R. Verhoeven and R. P. Volante, EP Pat. 137445/1990 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1985, 103, 160311).